
People's Perception about Tourism Branding of Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract: Cox's Bazar is one of the most attractive places as a tourist spot located in Chittagong Division of Bangladesh. It is known to all that Cox's Bazar is the longest sea beach in the world and it is a prime tourist spot at Bangladesh. The aim of this study is to identify the present brand image of Cox's Bazar among the national and international tourists. Besides, this study emphasizes the factors that persuade and can be used to build brand image of this spot and find out some new strategy to create and establish national and international brand image of Cox's Bazar. Methodology: This study is purposive in nature. Both national and international visitors were the respondents of this study. Data was collected from the 200 research respondents. This study finds a significant relationship between image branding and tourist destinations. Same factors as awareness, image, quality and loyalty play important in branding image of this tourist spot.

Keywords: Brand Image; Tourism Branding; Public awareness; Brand Quality; Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

Bangladesh's tourism industry is one of its most lucrative (Alam, 2018; Elena et al., 2012). The WTTC (2015) reports that, in comparison to US\$121.14 million in 2013, the tourism sector's contribution to Bangladesh's economy in 2014 was approximately US\$150 million. Bangladesh's tourism revenue increased significantly from USD 79 million in 2006 to USD 344 million in 2017, USD 214.3 million in 2016, and USD 150.3 million in 2015. Tourist arrivals were 643,094 in 2015 and 830,068 in 2016 (CEIC, 2019). Between 2009 and 2017, there were, on average, 552,500 foreign visitors to Bangladesh per year (Hossain & Wadood, 2019). From the middle of the 1990s until the present, Bangladesh's tourism industry has been steadily growing. Utilizing innovative methods and techniques presents a remarkable opportunity to develop a tourism market (Lincoln, 2019; Ullah, 2014). By supporting three of the top priorities for developing nations, the tourism industry can significantly contribute to economic development (Rahman et al., 2019; Haque, 2016). The 120km long uninterrupted sandy beach in Cox's Bazar is one of the world's natural wonders. Over 1.5 million tourists visit this capital city of Bangladesh each year, according to the Bangladesh Tourism Board (2016). Chittagong and Dhaka, the capital cities of Bangladesh with unspoiled sandy beaches, coconut palms, sunshine, and tropical weather, are connected to Cox's Bazar via road and air travel (Bhuiyan, 2017). Many think it's the perfect place to go on vacation (Tariq, 2017). The main places that people go are Labonee Beach, Himchori, Innani, and Cox's Bazaar's Kolatoli Point. Many hotels, motels, cottages, rest houses, and guest houses are available for lodging from Labonee Beach to Kolatoli Beach (Mahbub, 2019; Tariq, 2017).

This Bangladeshi capital city's tourism potential has already been demonstrated (Bhuiyan, 2017). Due to its low cost of living, Bangladesh has a great deal of potential as a cheap alternative to travel destinations like Bali, Indonesia, and Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. This location is the world's longest stretch of shark-free seashore and a strong candidate for the 2008 World's New 7 Natural Wonders competition (Zahra, 2012; WTTC, 2015). The majority of visitors to Cox's Bazar are from within the country; however, some visitors come from major tourist destination countries such as the UK, Korea, Japan, USA, India, Australia, Nepal, and Pakistan (Hossain, 2010). Every hotel, motel, and guest house in Cox's Bazar is completely booked up with tourists from November to March, which is considered the peak tourism season (Mahbub, 2019; Azam et al., 2010; Saleh, 2010). Bangladesh is facing a reputation problem, also called a "brand image crisis," despite having a lot of potential as a tourist destination. The restaurants near the seashore and in the hotel-motel area, which primarily serve food in Bangladeshi standards, are a major contributing factor to this (Tariq, 2017; Arif, 2011). Numerous

factors influence travelers' decisions to visit Bangladesh, according to earlier research. According to the study (Kamruzzaman, 2018; Azam, 2010), the intention to choose a tour destination in Bangladesh can be statistically explained by factors such as shopping facilities, natural beauty, security, and service quality.

One of the main factors influencing a region's touristic appeal is creating an image of it that reflects consumer preferences (Ksouri, et al., 2015). The Bangladeshi government has placed a strong emphasis on branding its travel industry. The government gave the Ministry of Tourism and Civil Aviation (Biman) BDT 3,688 core in FY2020–21 (Hasan, 2020). Cox's Bazaar can be branded as a destination through direct marketing, brochures, media partnerships, public relations, publicity, advertising websites, and cooperative destination branding associations (Tariq, 2017; Mahub, 2019). The overall goal is to investigate the state of Cox's Bazaar's brand image. The specific goals are to understand people's perceptions of Cox's awareness as a destination, as well as people's perceptions of the destination's image, the perceived quality of Cox's Bazaar as a tourist destination, and people's perceptions of the destination's loyalty.

2. Research Gap and rationale of this study

Bangladesh's most popular tourist destination is Cox's Bazar. Research on tourism facilities, potentials, investments, development plans, issues, and future prospects, as well as the effects of tourism on the local economy and society in Cox's Bazar, has already been done, according to a review of earlier tourism-related literature. The perception of the public towards Cox's Bazar's tourism branding has not been the subject of any research. This research gap is quite acute. Currently, national branding is a key idea for the growth of the tourism industry worldwide. As the country's official tourism organization, the Bangladesh Tourism Board (BTB) launched the nation branding campaign in 2008 with the catchy slogan "Beautiful Bangladesh" and the logo "Rising sun above the sea waves" (Safiullah, N. M., October 04, 2019). "Visit Bangladesh before others come" was a tourism slogan created a few years ago in Bangladesh, when the nation had very few foreign visitors. A country can gain a distinct competitive advantage by promoting a positive and strong national brand, which also increases exports, draws in foreign investment, and increases tourism. November 26, 2019 (Uddin, M. K.). In the Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Report (2019), Bangladesh is ranked 120th out of 140 countries in terms of the accessibility of tourist-friendly amenities like lodging, security, air travel, and cultural engagement. Nonetheless, the way that people view tourism branding plays a significant role in the industry's overall development. According to Lim and O'Cass (2001), a tourist destination that enjoys a strong image is more likely to be chosen and considered at the end of the decision-making process, as it can be more easily distinguished from its competitors. Consequently, a destination's image becomes one of its primary selling points and the factor that influences travelers' decisions the most when making travel plans (Lopes & Dominique 2011). Individual value systems eventually function as a selective attention filter to shape the perception that people have of a particular tourist destination (Moutinho, 1987). According to Bonn, Joseph, and Dai (2005), an individual's country of origin also affects the perception that they have of certain tourist sites. There are both material and immaterial components to every tourist destination. A destination's culture, customs, and history are considered intangible elements, whereas natural attractions like beaches and mountains or historical cultural heritage are considered tangible elements. Additionally, it is crucial to comprehend how people view Cox's Bazaar as the world's most perfect uninterrupted seashore in terms of branding.

3. Research Question

- Q.1. What is the people's perception on Destination Awareness of Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh?
- Q.2. What is the people's perception on Destination Image of Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh?
- Q.3. What is the perceived quality of Cox's Bazar as a tourist destination?
- Q.4. What is the people's perception on Destination loyalty of Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh?

4. Objectives of the study

Objectives of the study are as follows:

- a) The aim of this study is to identify the present brand image of Cox's Bazar among the national and international tourists.
- b) This study emphasizes the factors that persuade and can be used to build brand image of this spot and find out some new strategy to create and establish national and international brand image of Cox's Bazar.

5. Literature Review

In addition, images are a simplification of many associations and bits of information related to a destination (Lv et al., 2020; Stylos et al., 2016). The brand image is the culmination of all beliefs, ideas, and impressions that people associate with a destination. According to Josiassen et al. (2016), branding necessitates verbal and visual cues that highlight the name or logo that denotes a unique product or service. Therefore, whether a consumer's interpretation is rational or emotional, brand image is a perceptual phenomenon that is created by that process (Aulia & Briliana, 2017; Tekin et al., 2016). A number of destination studies that focus on visitors' perceptions use the crucial concept of branding (Gras, 2008). According to Kasapi and Cela (2017) and Ruiz-Real et al. (2020), a brand can be a potent tool in the creation of a successful destination. Destinations now rely on marketing communications to promote their brand identity and image to target audiences in order to highlight the unique qualities of their tourism brands and present a positive image of the

mentioned brand to a target market (Avraham & Ketter, 2016; Vinyals-Mirabent, 2018).

Since the key to a destination's success lies in what sets it apart from the others, image is a crucial component in tourism destination promotion (Carballo et al., 2015). A substantial corpus of research from the past 40 years has examined the role that an image plays in determining a particular tourism destination's level of success. A variety of studies have approached the subject from various angles (Deng & Li, 2014). A strategic approach to establishing a nation's image in the global market is a characteristic of national branding. Owing to growing competition and globalization, which favor the idea that certain nations are megabrands in need of efficient marketing to properly showcase them to investors, travelers, and decision-makers (Gorbaniuk & Radman, 2011). A relatively recent term that encompasses nation branding, region branding, and city branding is "branding of an area or place" (Suchitra, 2015). In the tourism industry, a strong brand image helps consumers form positive perceptions about visiting that specific location (Canovi & Pucciarelli, 2019; Lehto & Lehto, 2019). Image building is a part of destination branding and empirical research indicates that branding improves travelers' perceptions of the destination (Akgün et al., 2020; Souiden et al., 2017). The cultural and natural characteristics of a destination are crucial differentiators that set it apart from other comparable products (Baniya et al., 2017; Fraiz et al., 2020), and Cox's Bazar possesses these characteristics. As a tourist's decision-making process is greatly influenced by the visual image of a place, Hsu (2009) proposes that destination image is one of the essential elements of pull force. Since branding can help to distinguish destinations by forming a favorable perception of a place in travelers' minds, its role in tourism marketing has become increasingly significant. A tourism destination is characterized as a place, political jurisdiction, or major attraction that aims to offer guests a variety of enjoyable to unforgettable experiences (Viken & Granås, 2016; Bornhorsta et al., 2010).

The travel and tourism industry places a high priority on customer satisfaction with regard to the quality of services received during the vacation experience (Neal, 2003). In the absence of an efficient and effective transportation system, the tourism industry would collapse (Cook et al., 2007). One of the more important demand-side factors is accommodation, since they have a significant impact on the kinds of tourists that visit a place (Guttentag & Smith, 2017; Zervas et al., 2017). Furthermore, lodging offers crucial assistance to fulfill the broader purpose that drew the traveler to the location (Camilleri, 2018; Shi et al., 2019). The location's attractiveness, its historical significance, and its entertainment options all play important roles as tour attractions. To satisfy customers, it is necessary to offer a variety of services in each of those areas (Holloway & Humphreys, 2019; Truong et al., 2018). Temporary attractions that offer a range of sights, activities, and live entertainment venues are events like fairs and festivals (Cook et al., 2007). Historically, town visits have been a leisure activity, and town visits have played a vital role in the tourism industry for as long as cities have existed (Ramires et al., 2018). Other studies provided information on improving brand image in the travel industry. For example, Sayeda's (2017) study looks at the potential effects of mass tourism on the environment, culture, society, and economy in Bangladesh, especially with regard to Cox's Bazar and the surrounding areas. There are a few key research findings that need to be considered when branding Cox's Bazar as a tourist destination. Promotion is necessary to maintain the Cox's Bazar brand image. In today's fiercely competitive global market, where destinations are fighting for customers, developing a unique destination image has become crucial to making an impression (Qu, et. al., 2011). Marketers must first advertise or give tourists accurate information about Cox's Bazaar in order to draw them in. They can entice tourists to visit Cox's Bazaar by showcasing amenities such as lodging options, historical site visits, guaranteed security, food availability, hotel services, and so forth (Tariq, 2017). A communication technique that disseminates product information is advertising. The primary goal of advertising is to present a positive image of the product and actively encourage consumers to buy it. Recently, mobile and internet networks have been used to advertise tourism in a new way (Shaouf et al., 2016; Park et al., 2008). To maintain the destination's local identity, the community's and destination's true characteristics must be maintained (Tasci, et al., 2004).

6. Methodology

There was a purpose behind the study. It was decided to survey tourists visiting the city from abroad or from across the country who consented to participate. The questionnaires were administered in five well-known tourist destinations within the city, which are distinguished by a concentrated tourist offer and a higher volume of visitors. A 95% confidence level and a $\pm 7\%$ margin of error were used to define the sample size, and as a result, 196–200 visitors were surveyed at the five predetermined locations. In September 2019, a pilot test comprising 40 visitors was conducted to validate the final instrument through a pilot sampling of the instrument. However, we gathered the data from both domestic and foreign visitors equally.

6.1 Operationalization of the Variables

Authors in the fields of marketing (Yoo and Donthu, 2002) and tourism (Milman and Pizam, 1995) were taken into consideration for the operationalization of the awareness variables. Numerous empirical studies in tourism research (Hunt, 1975; Echtner and Ritchie, 1993; Baloglu and McCleary, 1999a and 1999b; Gallarza, Gil and Calderon, 2002; Konecnik, 2002 and 2004) have examined the tourism destination image, which encompasses the quality dimension. The brand loyalty

dimension was operationalized in accordance with the recommendations of prominent marketing scholars (Oliver, 1996) as well as writers who examined this dimension in the context of destination studies for tourism (Gitelson and Crompton, 1984; Bigne, Sanchez and Sanchez, 2001). Table 1 presents a thorough analysis of the sources of scale development.

Table 1: Source of scale development for the customer-based brand equity dimension for a tourism destination

Dimension	Source of Scale Development	Questions
Tourism destination awareness	Milman and Pizam (1995) Yoo and Donthu (2002)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I have heard of Cox's Bazar. I have difficulty imagining Cox's Bazar in my mind. Some characteristics about Cox's Bazar come quickly to my mind.
Tourism destination's image	Hunt (1975) Echtner and Ritchie (1993) Baloglu and McCleary (1999a and 1999b) Gallarza, Gil and Calderon (2002) Konecnik (2002 and 2004)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is beautiful nature at Cox's Bazar. There are good opportunities for recreational activities and events at Cox's Bazar. There is pleasant weather at Cox's Bazar. Cox's Bazar protects and maintains historical and cultural attractions very well.
Tourism destination's perceived quality	Hunt (1975) Echtner and Ritchie (1993) Baloglu and McCleary (1999a and 1999b) Baker and Crompton (2000) Gallarza, Gil and Calderon (2002) Konecnik (2002 and 2004)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a high level of cleanliness at Cox's Bazar. There is a high level of personal safety at Cox's Bazar. There is high quality of accommodation at Cox's Bazar. There is high quality of infrastructure at Cox's Bazar. There is appealing local food at Cox's Bazar. There is good value for money at Cox's Bazar. There is high quality of tourism services at Cox's Bazar. There are few problems with communication at Cox's Bazar
Tourism destination's loyalty	Gitelson and Crompton (1984) Fakeye and Crompton (1991) Oliver (1996) Oppermann (2000) Bigne, Sanchez and Sanchez (2001)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are low prices of tourism services at Cox's Bazar. I would like to visit Cox's Bazar again in the future. I intend to recommend Cox's Bazar to my friends. Cox's Bazar provides more benefits than other similar Bangladeshi tourism destinations. Cox's Bazar is one of the preferred tourism destinations I want to visit.

7. Data Analysis and Findings

Table 2: Socio-Demographic Status of the respondents: (n=200)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	150	75%
Female	50	25%
Age Group		
25-34 years	69	35%
35-44 years	96	48%
45-54 years	35	18%
Marital Status		
Single	90	45%
Married	110	55%
Educational Status		
Graduation	80	40%
Post-Graduation	120	60%
Expenditure on the Trip		
5000-10,000 Tk	47	24%
10001-20,000 Tk.	30	15%
20001-40,000 Tk.	27	14%
Over 40,000 Tk	96	48%

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents (Table 2) shows that, overall, 48% are between 35 and 44 years old, which means that is a young demand; 75% of the respondents were male and the other 25% were female. The majority were married (55%), 60% of the respondents were highly educated. Finally, the 48% reported expenditure on the trip was over BDT 40,000.

7.1 Reliability of instrument

Table 3 shows the results of the reliability analysis – Cronbach's Alpha Value. The test demonstrates the consistency between the measurement's scales used in the sixteen variables used in the research. A score of 1.0 on the Cronbach Alpha indicates 100 percent reliability. The score obtained from 0.753 is above the generally accepted score of Nunnally (1978) of 0.753; this result shows the reliability of the questionnaire.

Table 3: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Number of elements
0.753	20

7.2 Exploratory Factor Analysis

We ran the KMO and Bartlett's sphericity tests to see if the data were suitable for the exploratory factor analysis. According to Hair, Black, Babin, and Tatham (2006), factor analysis is helpful when paired with the provided data if the overall result is greater than 0.50. The fact that the value of 0.560 in this instance indicates that the data are suitable for factor analysis and validates that one is in fact necessary. The very low value of the level of significance (Sig. = 0.000) further suggests a high degree of correlation between the variables (Table 4).

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.560
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1766.296
	df	190
	Sig.	.000

Table 5 illustrates this process. By removing 20 variables that indicate the attributes of the Cox's Bazar brand, only initial eigenvalues greater than one (1) were considered, and the result was that four (4) representative uncorrelated components collectively explain 65.352% of the total variance over the perception. Since their combined explanation of the cumulative variance is only 34.648%, the remaining components with initial eigenvalues smaller than one (1) were eliminated.

Table 5: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.715	23.577	23.577	4.715	23.577	23.577	3.618	18.091	18.091
2	3.672	18.359	41.936	3.672	18.359	41.936	3.109	15.545	33.636
3	2.553	12.765	54.701	2.553	12.765	54.701	2.640	13.201	46.837
4	2.130	10.650	65.352	2.130	10.650	65.352	2.495	12.476	59.313
5	.967	8.139	73.491						
6	.952	5.403	78.894						
7	.944	4.719	83.613						
8	.786	3.928	87.541						
9	.579	2.896	90.437						
10	.514	2.570	93.007						
11	.365	1.823	94.830						
12	.240	1.198	96.028						
13	.213	1.067	97.095						
14	.147	.736	97.831						
15	.126	.631	98.462						
16	.116	.578	99.041						
17	.075	.375	99.416						
18	.055	.276	99.692						
19	.047	.236	99.928						
20	.014	.072	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Reducing the number of factors that have high loadings on the variables under study is the goal of rotation. The factors that set Cox's Bazar apart as a travel destination are highlighted by four components that are revealed by the Factor Analysis (Table 6). When variables that exhibit notable loads in the same factor are identified, common factors can be defined thanks to the rotated component matrix.

Table 6: Rotated Component Matrixa

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
I have heard of Cox's Bazar.	.921			
I have difficulty imagining Cox's Bazar in my mind.	.831			
Some characteristics about Cox's Bazar come quickly to my mind.	.774			
There is beautiful nature at Cox's Bazar		.931		
There are good opportunities for recreational activities and events at Cox's Bazar.		.709		
There is pleasant weather at Cox's Bazar.		.794		
Cox's Bazar protects and maintains historical and cultural attractions very well.		.635		
There is a high level of cleanliness at Cox's Bazar.			.717	
There is a high level of personal safety at Cox's Bazar.			.839	
There is high quality of accommodation at Cox's Bazar.			.845	
There is high quality of infrastructure at Cox's Bazar.			.775	
There is appealing local food at Cox's Bazar.			.653	
There is good value for money at Cox's Bazar.			.695	
There is high quality of tourism services at Cox's Bazar.			.830	
There are few problems with communication at Cox's Bazar			.811	
There are low prices of tourism services at Cox's Bazar.				.833
I would like to visit Cox's Bazar again in the future.				.779
I intend to recommend Cox's Bazar to my friends.				.944
Cox's Bazar provides more benefits than other similar Bangladeshi tourism destinations.				.928
Cox's Bazar is one of the preferred tourism destinations I want to visit.				.649
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.				
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.				
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.				

The first Component of relevance, which was called "Tourism Destination Awareness Factor", includes, in order of importance and its respective load factor, three variables: heard about the Cox's Bazar (.921), difficulty imaging on tourist mind (.831) and some special characteristic come on tourist mind (.774). By itself this factor account for a variance of 23.57%. The second Component determined as "Tourism Destination's Image Factor" contain aspects such as beautiful nature of the Cox's Bazar (.931), good opportunity of recreation (.709), pleasant weather (.794), history and culture of Cox's Bazar (.635) and it represents 18.36 % of the variance.

Thirdly, appears the Component named "Tourism Destination's Perceived Quality Factor", which cover aspects directly related to cleanliness (.717), safeties environment (.839), quality accommodation (.845), quality infrastructure (.775), appalling of local food (.653), quality hospitality services (.830), good value of money (.695), and some communication problem (.811), explaining the 12.77 % of the variance. The fourth Component called "Tourism Destination's Loyalty Factor" refers to the representative monuments of the city. Price sensitivity (.833), visit again (.779), recommended to other (.944), place benefit (.928) and personal interest (.649), explicating the 10.65% of the variance.

8. Discussion

This study gave gender a lot of consideration. The study's research respondents are both male and female. The male respondent's ratio is higher than the female's. Women make up 25% of respondents when men make up 75%. The respondent population is primarily composed of married, educated individuals, with a ration of roughly 55% and 60%. According to the study, Cox's trip to the Bazar cost between 5000 and 40000 BDT. Individual perceptions of image branding vary, and this study takes into account the respondents' gender, age, marital status, employment status, and level of education. The study also identifies four elements related to Cox's Bazar's branding image. The "Tourism Destination Awareness Factor," the first relevant component, accounts for 23.57% of the respondent's variance. Research has demonstrated that destination awareness plays a crucial role in the decisions and actions of tourists (Milman & Pizam, 1995).

The second component, which accounts for 18.36% of the variance, was identified as the "Image Factor of the Tourism Destination." Few longitudinal studies have been conducted, and most destination image studies have been cross-sectional. The need for research using experimental design to look at how variables like awareness, familiarity, image, and intent change over time results from this (Roberts, 2008). The third component, "Tourism Destination's Perceived Quality Factor," accounts for 12.77 percent of the variation. According to Ryglóvá et al. (2016), quality is increasingly emerging as a powerful competitive advantage in the era of global competition, when the entire spectrum of replacement products is available. According to Fornell et al. (1996), quality is a predictor of satisfaction.

An empirical analysis conducted on a sample of interpretive center visitors confirms that satisfaction is directly influenced by perceived quality (Campo-Martínez & Garau-Vadell, 2010). The "Loyalty Factor of Tourism Destinations" is the fourth component, and it explains 10.65% of the variation. Tourist loyalty at coastal or island-based destinations has been found to be significantly influenced by perceived value, satisfaction, and the quality of the service (Chen and Tsai, 2007). There are variables in every single factor. such as the lovely weather, Cox's Bazar's history and culture, cleanliness, first-rate lodging, first-rate infrastructure, the terrible local cuisine, the guest services, communication issues, price sensitivity, and so forth.

9. Limitations of the study and future research

Cronbach's Alpha Value was used in this study to measure the variables related to the research findings, and it is an effective method. Bartlett's sphericity test and KMO test were both successfully completed in this investigation. The small research sample that attended the Cox's bazaar, where participation by men and women is unequal, is the focus of this study. To better understand Bangladeshis' perceptions of Cox's Bazaar's branding, researchers will need to gather a vast amount of data from the country. There are no studies that have been found that address how people perceive Cox's Bazar's tourism branding or what the current state of the bazaar's brand image is as a destination. There is a paucity of literature on these particular subjects, so this work will help by providing references for further research in the future. Future research opportunities exist, and this paper will be a future addition to the body of knowledge regarding the branding image of Cox's Bazaar. Other possible concerns for promoting tourism in Cox's bazaar may be investigated in the future; however, the People's Perception about Tourism Branding of Cox's Bazar is the primary focus of this study.

10. Conclusion

This study examines how Cox's Bazaar is marketed as a tourist destination. One of Bangladesh's most popular tourist destinations is Cox's Bazar. Establishing a place's brand is a challenging undertaking. The only other option to make a destination well-known and popular throughout the world is to develop a branding image. The focus of this study is on the various elements and components that will contribute to the development of a positive brand image for Cox's Bazaar as a tourism destination. Several statistical techniques were employed in this study to determine the association between destination and image branding. The results of this study will contribute to enhancing Cox's Bazaar's reputation as a travel destination. One of the study's main conclusions is that respondents' perceptions of their own images differ statistically significantly depending on their age, gender, marital status, occupation, and level of education. Some strategies, like spreading good word about Cox's Bazaar, may be useful in promoting the event as a tourist destination. Those who have been to Cox's Bazaar are required to recommend it to others. Examine potential avenues for foreign tourists to visit Cox's Bazaar. International media promotion will be crucial to establishing Cox's Bazaar as a popular tourist destination. Organize national and international conferences centered on the Cox's Bazaar.

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